

On Covering Properties*)

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Using AULL's concept of an α -paracompact subset, the various axioms of separation and embeddings, we define in this paper some classes of topological spaces: the classes $\Gamma^*(T_i)$ for each $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4, 5, 5a$ and $\Gamma^*(T_j^*)$ for each $j = 4, 5, 5a$. (Throughout this paper a T_3 space is a regular T_0 space, a T_{3a} space is a completely regular T_0 space, a T_4 space is a normal T_1 space, a T_5 space is a hereditarily normal T_1 space, a T_{5a} space is a perfectly normal T_0 space, a T_4^* space is a collectionwise normal T_1 space, a T_5^* space is a hereditarily collectionwise normal T_1 space and a T_{5a}^* space is a T_5^* space in which all closed subsets are G_δ (Cf. [4] II)).

These classes allow us to give characterizations of compact, LINDELÖF and paracompact spaces in the realm of T_2 spaces. In fact: "a T_{3a} space is compact if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_{3a} space in which it is embedded as a closed subset" (Proposition 1.2), "a T_4 space is LINDELÖF if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_4 space in which is embedded as a closed subset" (Proposition 1.11) and "a collectionwise normal T_1 space is paracompact if and only if it is α -paracompact in each collectionwise normal T_1 space in which is embedded as a closed subset" (Proposition 1.16).

Analogously, we define in Section 2 of this paper the classes $\Pi^*(T_i)$ (for each $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4, 5, 5a$) and $\Pi^*(T_j^*)$ (for each $j = 4, 5, 5a$) related to TELGÁRSKY's class Π^* .

1. The classes $\Gamma^*(T_i)$ and $\Gamma^*(T_j^*)$

C. E. AULL defined in [1] the notion of an α -paracompact subset. A subset E of a topological space X is said to be α -paracompact in X if every covering of E by open subsets of X has a refinement by open subsets of X which is locally finite in X and which covers E . α -paracompact subsets have been studied in [1] and [3]. Using this

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concept and the various axioms of separation we shall define some classes of topological spaces. These classes give characterizations of compact, LINDELÖF, and paracompact spaces in the realm of T_2 spaces.

Definition 1. For every $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4, 5, 5a$, we shall denote by $\Gamma^*(T_i)$ the class of all T_i spaces which are α -paracompact in each T_i space in which are embedded as closed subsets.

Definition 2. For every $j = 4, 5, 5a$, we shall denote by $\Gamma^*(T_j^*)$ the class of all T_j^* spaces which are α -paracompact in each T_j^* space in which are embedded as closed subsets.

Remark. If C is the class of compact T_2 spaces then $C \subset \Gamma^*(T_2) \subset \Gamma^*(T_3) \subset \Gamma^*(T_{3a}) \subset \Gamma^*(T_4) \subset \Gamma^*(T_4^*)$.

1.1 Proposition. *The classes C , $\Gamma^*(T_2)$, $\Gamma^*(T_3)$ and $\Gamma^*(T_{3a})$ coincide.*

Proof. It suffices to show that $\Gamma^*(T_{3a}) \subset C$. Let X be a paracompact T_2 space. If $X \notin C$ then X is not countably compact and the discrete space of natural numbers $\mathbb{N}$ is embedded in X as a closed subset. Let j be the embedding of $\mathbb{N}$ in X .

Let $X \in \Gamma^*(T_{3a})$, let Z be a T_{3a} space such that $\mathbb{N}$ is embedded in Z as closed subset, let $Z + X$ be the topological sum, let $j_1: Z \hookrightarrow Z + X$, $j_2: X \hookrightarrow Z + X$ be the embeddings and let $Z \cup_j X$ be the adjunction space determined by Z , X and j . Since Z and X are T_2 , and the natural quotient mapping $q: Z + X \rightarrow Z \cup_j X$ is perfect, then $Z \cup_j X$ is completely regular. Let C be a closed subset of $Z \cup_j X$ and $p \in Z \cup_j X$ such that $p \notin C$. Then $q^{-1}(C) \cap q^{-1}(p) = \emptyset$. If $p \in q(j_1(Z \setminus \mathbb{N}))$ there exists a continuous mapping $f_1: j_1(Z) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f_1((q^{-1}(C) \cap j_1(Z)) \cup j_1(\mathbb{N})) = \{0\}$ and $f_1(t) = 1$ (where $q(t) = p$). The continuous mapping $f: Z + X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f|_{j_1(Z)} = f_1$ and $f|_{j_2(X)} \equiv 0$ defines a continuous mapping $\bar{f}: Z \cup_j X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\bar{f}(C) = \{0\}$ and $\bar{f}(p) = 1$. If $p \in q(j_2(X \setminus \mathbb{N}))$ the proof is similar to the above because X is T_{3a} . If $p = q(j_1(n)) = q(j_2(n))$ where $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists a continuous mapping $f_1: j_1(Z) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f_1(j_1(n)) = 1$ and $f_1((q^{-1}(C) \cap j_1(Z)) \cup j_1(\mathbb{N} \setminus \{n\})) = \{0\}$ and there exists a continuous mapping $f_2: j_2(X) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f_2(j_2(n)) = 1$ and $f_2((q^{-1}(C) \cap j_2(X)) \cup j_2(X \setminus \{n\})) = \{0\}$ then the continuous mapping $f: Z + X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f|_{j_1(Z)} = f_1$ and $f|_{j_2(X)} = f_2$ defines a continuous mapping $\bar{f}: Z \cup_j X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\bar{f}(C) = \{0\}$ and $\bar{f}(p) = 1$. Thus $Z \cup_j X$ is T_{3a} .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} Z & \xrightarrow{q \circ j_1} & Z \cup_j X \\ \cup & & \uparrow q \circ j_2 \\ \mathbb{N} & \hookrightarrow & X \end{array}$$

Since $q \circ j_2: X \rightarrow Z \cup_j X$ is a homeomorphic embedding, $(q \circ j_2)(X)$ is α -paracompact in $Z \cup_j X$. Let $\mathcal{U}$ be a covering of $\mathbb{N}$ by open subsets of Z , then $\{(q \circ j_1)(U) \mid U \in \mathcal{U}\}$ is a covering of $(q \circ j_1)(\mathbb{N})$ by open subsets of $(q \circ j_1)(Z)$. For every $U \in \mathcal{U}$ there exists an open subset U^* of $Z \cup_j X$ such that $U^* \cap (q \circ j_1)(Z) = (q \circ j_1)(U)$. Let $\mathcal{U}^*$ be the family of these subsets U^* , there is a refinement $\mathcal{W}$ of $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{U}^* \cup \{(Z \cup_j X) \setminus (q \circ j_1)(\mathbb{N})\}$ locally finite in $Z \cup_j X$ which covers $(q \circ j_2)(X)$ by open subsets of $Z \cup_j X$. The family $\{W \cap (q \circ j_1)(Z) \mid W \in \mathcal{W}, W \cap (q \circ j_1)(\mathbb{N}) \neq \emptyset\}$ is locally finite in $(q \circ j_1)(Z)$ and covers

$(q \circ j_1)(N)$ by open subsets of $(q \circ j_1)(Z)$. Finally

$$\mathcal{V} = \{(q \circ j_1)^{-1}(W \cap (q \circ j_1)(Z)) \mid W \in \mathcal{W}, W \cap (q \circ j_1)(N) \neq \emptyset\}$$

is a refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ by open subsets of Z , locally finite in Z , which covers N .

Thus, N is a member of the class $\Gamma^*(T_{3a})$. Let ω be the initial number of cardinality $\aleph_0$, let Ω be the smallest uncountably ordinal number and let $\omega' = [0, \omega]$ and $\Omega' = [0, \Omega]$. The space $T = \Omega' \times \omega' \setminus \{(\Omega, \omega)\}$ is called the TYCHONOFF plank. $A = \{\Omega\} \times [0, \omega)$ and $B = [0, \Omega) \times \{\omega\}$ are closed subsets of T which are not strongly separated, then A is not an α -paracompact subset in T (Theorem 1.3 in [3]). Since A is homeomorphic to N and T is T_{3a} , is $N \notin \Gamma^*(T_{3a})$. The contradiction follows from the hypothesis " X is a member of $\Gamma^*(T_{3a})$ ". Hence, if X is paracompact, T_2 space and $X \notin C$ then $X \notin \Gamma^*(T_{3a})$, i.e.: $\Gamma^*(T_{3a}) \subset C$.

1.2. Proposition. *A T_i space is compact if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_i space in which it is embedded as a closed subset. (For every $i = 2, 3, 3a$).*

1.3. Remark. $\Gamma^*(T_4) \neq C$. In fact $N \notin C$ and N is α -paracompact in each T_4 space Z such that N is embedded in Z as a closed subset (by b) of 1.3 in [3]).

1.4. Proposition. *If X is a LINDELÖF T_3 space then $X \in \Gamma^*(T_4)$.*

Proof. The proposition follows from b) of 1.3. in [3].

1.5. Proposition. *If $X \in \Gamma^*(T_4)$ and Y is closed subset of X then $Y \in \Gamma^*(T_4)$.*

Proof. Remark that Y is T_4 and let Z be a T_4 space such that Y is embedded in Z as a closed subset. Let $j: Y \rightarrow X$ be the embedding of Y in X and let $q: Z + X \rightarrow Z \cup_j X$ be the natural quotient mapping onto the adjunction space determined by Z , X and j . Since q is a perfect mapping, $Z \cup_j X$ is T_4 . Then $(q \circ j_2)(X)$ is α -paracompact in $Z \cup_j X$ and (analogously to the proof of 1.1) Y is α -paracompact in Z .

1.6. Proposition. *Let X be a paracompact T_1 space. Then X is a LINDELÖF space if and only if for every cardinal number $\aleph > \aleph_0$ the discrete space of cardinality, $\aleph, D(\aleph)$ is not embedded in X as a closed subset.*

Proof. If X is a LINDELÖF space and $\aleph > \aleph_0$, $D(\aleph)$ is not embedded in X as a closed set since a closed subset of a LINDELÖF space is LINDELÖF.

Conversely, let X be a paracompact space. Then X is a LINDELÖF space iff for every open covering of X there exists an open, locally finite, and countable refinement. Thus, if X is a paracompact T_1 space and is not a LINDELÖF space, there exists an open covering $\mathcal{U}_0$ of X such that any open refinement of $\mathcal{U}_0$ which is locally finite is not countable. Let $\mathcal{V} = \{V_j\}_{j \in J}$ be an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}_0$ which is locally finite. Then $\text{card}(J) > \aleph_0$. For each V_j which is non-empty pick by the axiom of choice, $x_j \in V_j$. Then $\{x_j\}_{j \in J}$ is a closed subset of X (because X is a T_1 space and $\mathcal{V}$ is locally finite). Then $\{x_j\}_{j \in J}$ is a discrete space of cardinality $\text{card}(J)$

1.7. Proposition. $\Gamma^*(T_4)$ is the class of LINDELÖF T_3 spaces.

Proof. For any $\aleph > \aleph_0$, $D(\aleph) \notin \Gamma^*(T_4)$. In fact for every $\aleph > \aleph_0$ exists a T_3 space X such that $D(\aleph)$ is closed in X and there is not a family $\{G_j\}_{j \in J}$ of pairwise disjoint open subsets of X such that $\{j\} \subset G_j$ for every $j \in D(\aleph)$ (X is the BRNG space, see [2] pp. 381–382 or [4] II pp. 100–102). Then it follows from Corollary 11B of [1] that $D(\aleph)$ is not α -paracompact in X .

Let $Z \in \Gamma^*(T_4)$. Then Z is a paracompact T_3 space. From 1.6 and 1.5 and the above paragraph it follows that Z is a LINDELÖF space.

The fact that every LINDELÖF T_3 space is in $\Gamma^*(T_4)$ was proved in 1.4.

1.8. Proposition. *Let X be a topological space. Then X is a LINDELÖF T_{5a} space if and only if X is a hereditarily LINDELÖF T_3 space.*

Proof. If X is a LINDELÖF T_{5a} space then X is T_3 and if G is an open subset of X , $G = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} F_n$ where F_n is closed for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then G is a LINDELÖF space and every subspace of X is a LINDELÖF space.

Conversely, let X be a hereditarily LINDELÖF T_3 space. Then X is T_4 and for every closed subset F of X and each $x \in X \setminus F$ there exists an open neighbourhood V^x of x such that $\overline{V^x} \cap F = \emptyset$. Thus $X \setminus F = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \overline{V^{x_n}}$, and $F = \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} (X \setminus \overline{V^{x_n}})$ for some sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $X \setminus F$. Hence, X is T_{5a} .

1.9. Proposition. 1) $\Gamma^*(T_5)$ is the class of LINDELÖF T_5 spaces.

2) $\Gamma^*(T_{5a})$ is the class of hereditarily LINDELÖF T_3 spaces.

Proof. If X is a LINDELÖF T_5 space (hereditarily LINDELÖF T_3 space) then $X \in \Gamma^*(T_4)$ and X is hereditarily normal (perfectly normal), thus $X \in \Gamma^*(T_5)$ ($X \in \Gamma^*(T_{5a})$).

Since T_5 and T_{5a} spaces are invariants of perfect mappings and the generalized BING spaces (see [4] II p. 128) are T_5 and T_{5a} but are not collectionwise normal, analogously to 1.5 and 1.7, the assertion follows.

1.10. Remark. $\Gamma^*(T_4) \supset \Gamma^*(T_5) \supset \Gamma^*(T_{5a})$ and these three classes are distinct. In fact: the cube $[0, 1]^{\mathbb{R}}$ is a member of $\Gamma^*(T_4)$ which is not in $\Gamma^*(T_5)$ and the space $[0, \Omega]$ is a member of $\Gamma^*(T_5)$ which is not in $\Gamma^*(T_{5a})$.

1.11. Proposition. *A T_j space is a LINDELÖF space if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_j space in which it is embedded as a closed subset (For every $j = 4, 5, 5a$).*

1.12. Remark. There are spaces in the class $\Gamma^*(T_4^*)$ which are not LINDELÖF spaces. In fact, for each $\aleph > \aleph_0$, $D(\aleph) \in \Gamma^*(T_4^*)$ because $D(\aleph)$ is T_4^* and if X is a T_4^* space in which $D(\aleph)$ is a closed subset, there exists a discrete family $\{A_j\}_{j \in D(\aleph)}$ of open subsets of X such that $\{j\} \subset A_j$ for each $j \in D(\aleph)$, then $\bigcup_{j \in D(\aleph)} \{j\} = D(\aleph)$ is α -paracompact in X (1.1 in [3]).

1.13. Proposition. *Let X be a regular space and E a subset of X . Suppose*

- a) E is weakly paracompact,
- b) E is an α -collectionwise normal subset in X ([1]) and
- c) for every open subset U of X such that $E \subset U$ there is an open subset V of X such that $E \subset V \subset \overline{V} \subset U$.

Then, E is α -paracompact in X .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U}$ be a covering of E by open subsets of X . There exists a point-finite refinement $\mathcal{O}^*$ of $\mathcal{U}^* = \{U \cap E \mid U \in \mathcal{U}, U \cap E \neq \emptyset\}$ by open subsets of E , which covers E .

For each $V \cap E \in \mathcal{O}^*$ there is $U_V \cap E \in \mathcal{U}^*$ such that $V \cap E \subset U_V \cap E$. Let $\mathcal{O} = \{V \cap U_V \mid V \cap E \in \mathcal{O}^*, U_V \cap E \in \mathcal{U}^*, V \cap E \subset U_V \cap E\}$. Clearly, $\mathcal{O}$ is a refinement of

$\mathcal{U}$ by open subsets of X and is point-finite in E . We denote $\mathcal{O} = \{0_s\}_{s \in S}$. Analogously to the proof of the Theorem of MICHAEL-NAGAMI ([2] pp. 400–401) for each $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ there is a discrete family $\{A_T\}_{T \in \mathcal{F}_{k+1}}$ of closed subsets of E such that $A_T \subset 0_{s_T}$ for some $0_{s_T} \in \mathcal{O}$. As E is α -collectionwise normal in X , for each $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, there exists a discrete family $\{G_T\}_{T \in \mathcal{F}_{k+1}}$ of open subsets of X such that $G_T \supset A_T$ for every $T \in \mathcal{F}_{k+1}$. For each $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and for each $T \in \mathcal{F}_{k+1}$, let $V_T = G_T \cap 0_{s_T}$. Then $\mathcal{V}_{k+1} = \{V_T\}_{T \in \mathcal{F}_{k+1}}$ is a discrete family of open subsets of X and $\bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{V}_i = \mathcal{V}$ is a refinement of $\mathcal{U}$, σ -discrete in X , by open subsets of X , which covers E . Moreover, we have the hypothesis c). From Theorem 1.3 in [3] it follows that E is α -paracompact in X .

1.14. Proposition. *If X is a paracompact T_2 space then $X \in \Gamma^*(T_4^*)$.*

Proof. The Proposition follows from 1.13.

1.15. Proposition. *$\Gamma^*(T_4^*)$ is the class of paracompact T_2 spaces.*

1.16. Proposition. *A collectionwise normal T_1 space is a paracompact space if and only if it is α -paracompact in each collectionwise normal T_1 space in which it is embedded as a closed subset.*

1.17. Proposition. 1) $\Gamma^*(T_5^*)$ is the class of paracompact T_5^* spaces. 2) $\Gamma^*(T_{5a}^*)$ is the class of hereditarily paracompact T_2 spaces in which all closed subsets are G_δ (which is the class of paracompact T_{5a} spaces).

Proof. 1) Follows from 1.14.

2) Clearly $\Gamma^*(T_{5a}^*)$ is the class of paracompact T_{5a} spaces. If X is a paracompact T_{5a} space, for every open subset G of X , G is F_σ . Hence G is paracompact and X is hereditarily paracompact. Hence, X is hereditarily collectionwise normal. The converse is obvious.

1.18. Remark. $\Gamma^*(T_4^*) \supset \Gamma^*(T_5^*) \supset \Gamma^*(T_{5a}^*)$ and these three classes are distinct. In fact: the ALEXANDROFF compactification X^* of $D(\mathfrak{M})$ (where $\mathfrak{M} > \aleph_0$) is a member of $\Gamma^*(T_5^*)$ which is not in $\Gamma^*(T_{5a}^*)$ (because X^* is T_5 and hereditarily paracompact and is not T_{5a}), and the cube $[0, 1]^{\mathbb{R}}$ is a member of $\Gamma^*(T_4^*)$ which is not in $\Gamma^*(T_5^*)$.

1.19. Proposition. *A T_j^* space is paracompact if and only if it is an α -paracompact subset in each T_j^* space in which it is embedded as a closed subset. (For every $j = \bar{5}, 5a$)*

2. The classes $\Pi^*(T_i)$ and $\Pi^*(T_j^*)$

R. TELGÁRSKY in [5] defined the concept of a well-situated subset. A subset E of a topological space X is said to be well-situated in X if for every paracompact T_2 space Y , $E \times Y$ is α -paracompact in $X \times Y$. Moreover, he denoted (in [5]) by Π^* the class of all paracompact T_2 spaces which are well-situated in each paracompact T_2 space in which they are embedded as closed subsets. We shall define some classes of topological spaces related to the class Π^* .

Definition 3. For every $i = 2, 3a, 3, 4, \bar{5}, 5a$ we shall denote by $\Pi^*(T_i)$ the class of all T_i spaces which are well-situated in each T_i space in which they are embedded as closed subsets.

Definition 4. For every $j = 4, 5, 5a$, we shall denote $\Pi^*(T_j^*)$ the class of all T_j^* spaces which are well-situated in each T_j^* space in which they are embedded as closed subsets.

2.1. Remarks. 1) a) For every $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4, 5, 5a$ we have $\Pi^*(T_i) \subset \Gamma^*(T_i)$. b) For every $j = 4, 5, 5a$ we have $\Pi^*(T_j^*) \subset \Gamma^*(T_j^*)$.

2) For every $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4$ we have $\Pi^*(T_i) \subset \Pi^*$ and $\Pi^*(T_4^*) \subset \Pi^*$.

2.2. Proposition. *The classes C , $\Pi^*(T_2)$, $\Pi^*(T_3)$ and $\Pi^*(T_{3a})$ coincide.*

Proof. Clearly $\Pi^*(T_2) \subset \Pi^*(T_3) \subset \Pi^*(T_{3a}) \subset \Gamma^*(T_{3a}) = C$.

We shall show that $C \subset \Pi^*(T_2)$. Let X be a compact T_2 space. Let Z be a T_2 space such that X is embedded as a closed subset in Z and let Y be any paracompact T_2 space. Let $\mathcal{A}$ be any covering of $X \times Y$ by open subsets of $Z \times Y$. For each $y \in Y$ and for each $x \in X$ there is an open neighbourhood V_y^z of x in Z and there is an open neighbourhood V_x^y of y in Y such that $V_y^z \times V_x^y$ is contained in some member of $\mathcal{A}$, whence there are $x_1(y), \dots, x_{n(y)}(y)$ such that $X \subset V_{x_1(y)}^z \cup \dots \cup V_{x_{n(y)}(y)}^z$ let $V^y = V_{x_1(y)}^z \cap \dots \cap V_{x_{n(y)}(y)}^z$. Thus, there is an open refinement $\mathcal{V} = \{V_j^y\}_{j \in J}$ of $\{V^y\}_{y \in Y}$, locally finite in Y . For each $j \in J$ we pick a $y_j \in Y$ such that $V_j \subset V^{y_j}$. Clearly $\bigcup_{j \in J} \{V_j^z \times V_j^y\}$ is a refinement of $\mathcal{A}$, by open subsets of $Z \times Y$, locally finite in $Z \times Y$, which covers $X \times Y$.

2.3. Remarks. 1) $\Pi^*(T_4) \neq C$, 2) $\Pi^*(T_4) \neq \Gamma^*(T_4)$, 3) $\Pi^*(T_4) \subsetneq \Pi^*(T_4^*)$, 4) $\Pi^*(T_4^*) \neq \Gamma^*(T_4^*)$.

Proofs. 1) $N \in \Pi^*(T_4)$. For let Z be a T_4 space such that N is closed subset in Z . Then N is α -paracompact in Z by 1.4. Thus, there exists a family $\{G_n\}_{n \in N}$ of open subsets of Z , discrete in Z such that $n \in G_n$ for each $n \in N$ (Corollary 11B in [1]). Then, for any paracompact T_2 space Y , $\{G_n \times Y\}_{n \in N}$ is a discrete family which covers $N \times Y$ by open subsets of $Z \times Y$. Since $\{n\} \in \Pi^*(T_2)$ for each $n \in N$, $\{n\}$ is well-situated in Z for each $n \in N$. Hence N is well-situated in Z .

2) The space of rational numbers $\mathbb{Q}$ is a member of the class $\Gamma^*(T_4)$ (Proposition 1.4) but $\mathbb{Q} \notin \Pi^*(T_4)$ because $\mathbb{Q} \notin \Pi^*$ ([5]).

3) Obviously $\Pi^*(T_4) \subset \Pi^*(T_4^*)$. Moreover $D(\mathfrak{M})$, where $\mathfrak{M} > \aleph_0$ is a member of the class $\Pi^*(T_4^*)$ and is not a member of the class $\Pi^*(T_4)$, because $D(\mathfrak{M})$ where $\mathfrak{M} > \aleph_0$ is not a LINDELÖF space.

4) $\mathbb{Q} \in \Gamma^*(T_4^*)$ and $\mathbb{Q} \notin \Pi^*(T_4^*)$.

Notes. R. TELGÁRSKY in [5] defined and studied the notion of a C -scattered space. X is said to be C -scattered if for each non-void closed subset E of X there is a point $x \in E$ and an open neighbourhood U^x of x for which $\overline{U^x} \cap E$ is compact. Also he denoted (in [6]) by SC the class of all C -scattered spaces.

2.4. Proposition. *For every $i = 4, 5, 5a$, we have $\Gamma^*(T_i) \cap SC = \Pi^*(T_i)$ and for every $i = 4, 5, 5a$, we have $\Gamma^*(T_i^*) \cap SC \subset \Pi^*(T_i^*)$.*

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Theorem 2.3 of TELGÁRSKY ([5]). Let X be a C -scattered space which belongs to $\Gamma^*(T_i)$ ($\Gamma^*(T_i^*)$). The proof proceeds by transfinite induction.

If $X^{(0)} = \emptyset$, then $X = \emptyset$ and hence the assertion is true.

If $X^{(\alpha+1)} = \emptyset$, then $X^{(\alpha)}$ is locally compact and by Theorem 1.6 of TELGÁRSKY ([5]) there is a locally finite closed covering $\{R_j\}_{j \in J}$ of X such that every $R_j^{(\alpha)}$ is compact.

Let Z be a T_i space (T_i^* space) in which X is a closed subset. Then $\{R_j\}_{j \in J}$ is locally finite in Z and X is α -paracompact in Z . Hence (by Proposition 1.5 of [3]) there exists a family $\{V_j\}_{j \in J}$ of open subsets of Z , locally finite in Z , such that $R_j \subset V_j$ for each $j \in J$. Thus, for any paracompact T_2 space Y , $\{V_j \times Y\}_{j \in J}$ is a locally finite family of open subsets of $Z \times Y$, which covers $X \times Y$. It suffices to prove that each R_i is well-situated in Z . To simplify the notation let us put $F = R_i$. Let $\mathcal{A}$ be any open covering of $F \times Y$ in $Z \times Y$. For each $y \in Y$ the set $F^{(\alpha)} \times \{y\}$ is compact; hence there is an open subset U_y of Z and an open subset V^y of Y such that

$$F^{(\alpha)} \times \{y\} \subset U_y \times V^y \subset \overline{U_y} \times \overline{V^y} \subset \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{A}_y} A$$

where $\mathcal{A}_y$ is some finite subfamily of $\mathcal{A}$. Clearly, $\{V^y\}_{y \in Y}$ is an open covering of Y . Let $\mathcal{B}$ be an open, locally finite refinement of $\{V^y\}_{y \in Y}$. We may assume that $\mathcal{B}$ is irreducible. For each $B \in \mathcal{B}$ we pick a $y_B \in Y$ such that $B \subset V^{y_B}$ and $\{V^{y_B}\}_{B \in \mathcal{B}}$ is also a covering of Y , then it has a shrinking $\mathcal{B}^*$ such that for each $B \in \mathcal{B}$ there is $B' \in \mathcal{B}^*$ such that $\overline{B'} \subset B$. Since $F^{(\alpha)} \subset U_{y_B}$, we have $(F \setminus U_{y_B})^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$. Hence, by the inductive assumption, $F \setminus U_{y_B}$ is well-situated in Z . Then there exists a refinement $\mathcal{C}_B$ of $\mathcal{A}$, by open subsets of $Z \times Y$, locally finite in $Z \times Y$, which covers $(F \setminus U_{y_B}) \times B$ and such that $\bigcup_{C \in \mathcal{C}_B} C \subset Z \times B$. Thus,

$$\{(U_{y_B} \times B) \cap A \mid A \in \mathcal{A}_{y_B}, B \in \mathcal{B}\} \cup \left(\bigcap_{B \in \mathcal{B}} \mathcal{C}_B \right)$$

is a refinement of $\mathcal{A}$ by open subsets of $Z \times Y$, locally finite in $Z \times Y$, which covers $F \times Y$.

If $X^{(\alpha)} = \emptyset$ for the ordinal limit number α , then by Theorem 1.6 of [5] there is a locally finite closed covering $\{R_j\}_{j \in J}$ of X such that for each $j \in J$ there is a $\beta < \alpha$ such that $R_j^{(\beta)} = \emptyset$.

Hence, every R_j is well-situated in Z by the inductive assumption. Thus from Proposition 1.5 in [3] it follows that X is well-situated in Z .

Problem 1. For every $i = 4, 5, 5a$, does the class $\Gamma^*(T_i) \cap SC$ coincide with the class $\Pi^*(T_i)$? (Analogous problem for $\Gamma^*(T_i^*)$).

Problem 2. For every $i = 4, 5, 5a$, does the class $\Pi^*(T_i)$ coincide with the class $\Gamma^*(T_i) \cap \Pi^*$? (Analogous problem for $\Gamma^*(T_i^*)$).

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